

Action-Aware Self-Supervised Learning

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Original objective of the work package

Our second work package within the ARENA project aimed to investigate the impact of binocular vision, versus monocular vision, for learning object representations. We conducted preliminary experiments for which we simulated biological binocular vision and applied a contrastive loss function between both monocular inputs. This was combined with the SLTT method developed in the first work package. When comparing learning with and without binocular vision, we did not find significant differences for learning object representations. Thus, our preliminary results do not support that binocular integration is important for object learning. While further studies are needed to confirm our conclusion, we decided to prioritize a more promising research axis that studies a key facet of object learning in children.

New objective of the work package

Sensorimotor theories state that embodied actions drive the construction of visual representation in biological systems. According to the sensorimotor contingency theory [O’regan et al. (2001)], biological systems understand objects by extracting the regularities between embodied actions executed on the object and the visual stimuli. For instance, the concept of a cup may derive from understanding how the cup visually changes when manipulating the cup. Sensorimotor learning may highlight different features from our SLTT model introduced in WP1: while SLTT extracts slowly changing visual features, incorporating embodied actions (e.g. objects manipulation) in the learning process may highlight visual features that rapidly change due to the action. Thus, the new objective of this work package is to extend our computational model to study how the knowledge of embodied actions during toddlers’ natural interactions with objects can shape their object representations and explain psychophysical results.

Incorporating Action Information

In a first work by Xu and Triesch (2023), we present a new model called CIPER that goes beyond time-based augmentation to learn invariances. This model has access to the *actions* that were performed to change from one view of an object to the next (and which can be thought of as yet another modality). CIPER leverages this information to also learn an inverse model, i.e., predict what action turns one view of an object into another. This is shown to lead to quantifiable advantages in the learned representations.

The work by Aubret et al. (2025) called *Action-Aware Self-Supervised Learning (AA-SSL)* follows a similar approach, but instead of learning an inverse model it learns to align a representation of the action with a concatenation of the latent representations of the two object views. They show that this aids in aligning the representations of different object instances such that, e.g., a side view of a particular chair becomes aligned with the side

views of other chairs in the latent representation space. Together, the models by Xu and Triesch (2023) and Aubret et al. (2025) demonstrate the potential of incorporating action information when learning object representations and set the stage for creating models of the development of mental rotation abilities in children.

SLTT and AA-SSL jointly explain the performance of children in mental rotation tasks

In Aubret et Triesch. (2025), we explored whether AA-SSL can account for children's looking time in object recognition tasks. We simulated different experimental paradigms that aim to assess the use of mental rotations in children for recognizing an object from a rotated version of the same object and another object. We derived two object recognition strategies. In the first one, the simulated child simply compares the similarity between latent representations of views. In the second one, the child tries to recover the rotation executed between two views of an object. The results show that the model can use these strategies to recognize objects in different tasks, suggesting that children do not need actual mental rotations for solving what have been called "mental rotation tasks".

Conclusion

We explored how children leverage action to learn object representations and recognize objects and developed computational models that significantly improves over SLTT. In the next step, we plan to apply the model on in-the-wild visuo-motor data recorded on humans. This will allow us to assess the impact of daily motor actions on object representations, presenting the first validation of sensorimotor theories of visual learning at scale. We further plan to extend our model to learn to perform mental rotations and explore whether it can boost object recognition, as found in adults.

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